

DEVELOPMENT OF A SYSTEM FOR EVALUATING THE PROFITABILITY OF BANK SHARES IN THE UZBEK STOCK MARKET

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Abstract: This study examines the specifics of assessing the profitability of bank shares in the Uzbek stock market, taking into account limited liquidity, low free float, and high price sensitivity to the actions of individual market participants. The necessity of a comprehensive approach is substantiated, combining fundamental analysis with the assessment of market liquidity, impulse dynamics, and the stability of market behavior.

An integrated system of indicators is proposed, including fundamental, liquidity, impulse, and entropy components. It is shown that the profitability of bank shares is determined not only by the financial performance of the issuer but also by market structure, the ability to execute trades, and the phase state of trading activity.

The proposed approach is aimed at the operational assessment of the investment and trading attractiveness of bank shares under the conditions of the Uzbek stock market.

Keywords: Uzbek stock market, bank shares, stock profitability, liquidity, free float, dividend yield, impulse dynamics, entropy analysis, investment attractiveness, market structure.

Аннотация: В работе рассматриваются особенности оценки доходности банковских акций на узбекском фондовом рынке с учетом ограниченной ликвидности, низкого free-float и высокой чувствительности цен к действиям отдельных участников. Обосновывается необходимость комплексного подхода, сочетающего фундаментальный анализ с оценкой рыночной ликвидности, импульсной динамики и устойчивости рыночного поведения. Предлагается интегральная система показателей, включающая фундаментальные, ликвидностные, импульсные и энтропийные компоненты. Показано, что доходность банковских акций определяется не только финансовыми результатами эмитента, но и структурой рынка, возможностью реализации позиции и фазовым состоянием торгов. Предложенный подход ориентирован на оперативную оценку инвестиционной и торговой привлекательности банковских акций в условиях узбекского фондового рынка.

Ключевые слова: фондовый рынок Узбекистана, банковские акции, доходность акций, ликвидность, free-float, дивидендная доходность, импульсная динамика, энтропийный анализ, инвестиционная привлекательность, рыночная структура.

Introduction

The Uzbek stock market is characterized by a relatively limited number of liquid issuers, high ownership concentration, and shallow trading depth [1–4]. A significant portion of shares in many companies is held by strategic owners; as a result, the free float remains limited. Under such conditions, even relatively small transactions may have a noticeable impact on market prices.

A key feature of the local market is the strong dependence of price dynamics on the behavior of individual large participants. The emergence of a dominant buyer or seller can generate prolonged price impulses that are not always directly associated with fundamental changes in the issuer itself. Limited market depth and a wide bid–ask spread further amplify volatility [5].

Literature Review

The banking sector occupies a special position in the Uzbek stock market due to relatively higher information transparency, strict supervision of banks by the Central Bank, regular publication of financial statements, the significant role of banks in the economy, and sustained investor interest. Bank shares, more often than those of other issuers, become the object of both investment and speculative activity. At the same time, bank stocks are particularly sensitive both to fundamental changes—such as profit growth, capital expansion, and dividend policy—and to market structure factors, including liquidity, free float, and demand concentration.

The profitability of bank shares is formed under the influence of several key components. The main one is capital gains, arising from the growth of bank profits, increases in equity capital, dividend expectations, and changes in market expectations. Under conditions of limited supply, even a moderate increase in demand can lead to a significant rise in market prices. An important component remains dividend yield, which is defined as:

$$DY = \frac{D}{P}(1),$$

where DY — dividend yield,

D — dividend per share,

P — market price.

At the same time, for investors not only the absolute amount of dividends is important, but also the stability of a bank's dividend policy. In addition, a significant role is played by returns arising from market revaluation, when a bank's market capitalization remains below its fundamentally justified levels for a prolonged period,

while changes in the structure of supply and demand lead to an accelerated increase in stock prices.

To formalize the proposed profitability assessment system, a multi-level integrated approach is appropriate, in which the final evaluation is not formed directly from heterogeneous analytical blocks, but through the prior construction of partial indices for each key direction of analysis.

At the first stage, partial integral indicators are calculated, similarly to those discussed in [6]. The fundamental index (F) is formed based on a set of financial parameters, including the price-to-book value ratio (P/BV), return on equity (ROE), profit growth rates, capital adequacy, and dividend yield.

The liquidity index (L) reflects the market realizability of returns and is determined through indicators such as average daily trading volume, free float, bid-ask spread, market depth, and concentration of large orders.

The impulse-dynamic index (I) characterizes current market activity and includes the speed of price changes, trend stability, acceleration of price movements, and features of accumulation or distribution phases.

The entropy index (E) is designed to assess the degree of orderliness in market behavior, the probability of continuation of the current price direction, and the level of uncertainty.

In particular, the fundamental block allows for the assessment of the long-term baseline potential profitability of bank shares and reflects the internal financial attractiveness of the stock, including the price-to-book value ratio (P/BV).

$$\frac{P}{BVPS} = \frac{\text{market price}}{\text{book value of the bank's equity per share}} \quad (\text{parameter x1})$$

$$ROE = \frac{\text{net profit}}{\text{shareholders' equity}} \quad (\text{parameter x2}) \text{ among others}$$

Additionally, profit growth rates, capital adequacy, and dividend policy may also be taken into account.

The liquidity block reflects the practical feasibility of realizing returns and includes average daily trading volumes, free float, bid-ask spread width, order book depth, and the concentration of large orders. It is liquidity that determines the extent to which potential fundamental returns can be realized under actual market conditions.

The impulse-dynamic block characterizes current market momentum and can be expressed through the rate of price change:

$$I \approx \Delta P / \Delta t, \quad (2)$$

where ΔP — price change over the time interval Δt .

In addition, trend stability, the speed of market supply absorption, acceleration of price movements, and the presence of accumulation or distribution phases are analyzed. This block allows for the identification of the moment when the market transitions into an active phase.

The entropy block assesses the degree of orderliness in market behavior, including the stability of the price direction, the probability of continuation of the prevailing trend, the level of uncertainty, and transitions between phases of growth, stagnation, and decline. A decrease in entropy may indicate the formation of a stable directional impulse, whereas its increase is more often associated with a phase of uncertainty or distribution.

Thus, each partial index represents a function of the corresponding set of parameters:

$$Lil(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m) \quad F = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \quad (3)$$

$$I = i(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_k) \\ E = e(q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n)$$

At the second stage, the final integrated stock return index is constructed:

$$R = \alpha F + \beta L + \gamma I + \delta E, \quad (4)$$

where R — is the final assessment of the potential return of the stock,

α — represents the weight of the fundamental factor,

β — represents the weight of liquidity,

γ — represents the weight of the impulse component,

δ — represents the weight of the entropy factor (market uncertainty level).

Here, α , β , γ , δ are weighting coefficients representing the significance of the corresponding indices, where:

$$\alpha + \beta + \gamma + \delta = 1,$$

which allows the proposed profitability assessment system to be expressed in the form of a weighted average, thereby making the resulting indicator interpretable, comparable, and manageable.

The proposed model makes it possible to account for both the fundamental attractiveness of bank shares and the practical feasibility of realizing returns under specific market conditions. The weighting coefficients may be adjusted depending on the investment strategy. For example, in a long-term investment approach, greater weight may be assigned to the fundamental and liquidity components, whereas in a short-term trading strategy, the importance of the impulse-dynamic and entropy factors increases.

The use of such an integrated model allows a transition from the isolated analysis of individual indicators to a unified system of quantitative assessment, more adequately reflecting the specifics of the Uzbek stock market, where actual returns are determined not only by the financial characteristics of the issuer, but also by market liquidity structure, participant behavior, and the phase state of the market.

Conclusion

Thus, the proposed system enables the assessment of bank shares at three interrelated levels: the fundamental potential of returns, the practical realizability of returns through liquidity, and the temporal window of realization through the impulse–entropy structure of the market.

For the Uzbek stock market, it is of fundamental importance not only to determine the intrinsic attractiveness of a stock but also to assess the feasibility of entering and exiting positions, the presence of an active market impulse, and the current phase of market behavior.

The proposed approach makes it possible to move from a static valuation of bank shares to a system for the operational assessment of their actual market returns.

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